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LITERATURE DATA OF PATHOMORPHOLOGY OF JOINT DISEASES IN HORSES

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ABSTRACT

A number of research works are devoted to the study of foot joint pathologies, their diagnosis and prevention. However, many issues of the etiopathogenesis of joint diseases in horses, as well as modern methods of diagnosis, are still not well studied.

Leg diseases in horses can be caused when the order of keeping them is violated, when vehicles are poorly equipped, and when they are in unsatisfactory condition. An important and important type of explant injury in horse breeding is sports horse lacerations. According to I.A. Kalashnik (1990), foot diseases appear 3-4 times a year in horses at the equestrian school, and up to 10 times in intensively loaded horses. Arthritis takes the first place among foot diseases in sports horses, accounting for 44% of all foot diseases, and takes the form of acute or chronic serous-fibrinous inflammation. [1]

According to K. I. Shakalov (1987), damage to vital tissues and organs develops with a large amount of blood loss, and acute injuries can pose a threat to the life of the animal. Traumatic poisoning of animals occurs as a result of large-scale closed injuries of tissues and the rapid absorption

of toxic substances into the blood resulting from tissue decomposition. Liver, stomach, intestines, urinary bladder and other organs may rupture as a result of traumas caused by strong mechanical factors, and as a result of pathogenic microorganisms falling into damaged tissues, in many cases as a complication of injuries. there is a risk of developing pathological processes such as abscess, phlegmon, necrobacteriosis, actinomycosis. In most cases, injured animals develop various types of neurotrophic disorders such as paralysis and semi-paralysis, atrophy, and death of nerve tissue, which can lead to deterioration of the general condition of the animal. Joint injuries differ from each other depending on the degree of progression, the complexity of the treatment process, and the consequences.

K.I. Shakalov and others (1987) stated that purulent inflammation of the joints is

due to various reasons, for example, puncture wounds, mechanical damage to the tissues around the joint, periarticular tissues, the mucous membrane of the synovial bag and develops as a result of the passage of purulent inflammatory processes through tendon sheaths to joint tissues, as well as metastatic passage in diseases such as pleurisy, endometritis, paraarthritis. According to the author's information, in purulent inflammation of the joints, mixed microflora characterized by the predominance of staphylococci and streptococci, as well as Escherichia coli and Pseudomonas aeruginosa are distinguished. [2]

According to V. M. Chepoy (1990), diseases of the surrounding tissues of the joint - tendon and tendon sheath (tendinitis and tendovaginitis), tendons (ligamentitis), the place of attachment of these elements to bones (enthesopathy), synovial bag (bursitis), are inflammations of aponeurosis and fascia (aponeurosis fasciitis), which have an inflammatory or degenerative character, and are caused by a closed injury or injury. As a result of these diseases, the movement of the joint is limited and it becomes painful. [5]

According to M.S. Borisov (1991), exudate contains vascular reactions that occur with the death of tissue cells that have died as a result of damage to the joint capsule, which leads to the stimulation of receptors. Such processes cause swelling of the synovial sheaths and their nipples. [4]

A.D. Belov, M.V. Plaxotin, B.A. Bashkirov (1990) and others say that purulent arthritis is a purulent inflammation of all the elements that make up the joint. The causes are the same as in purulent synovitis, that is, common pathogenic factors play a major role.

Purulent arthritis can be primary or secondary. Primary purulent arthritis is caused by penetrating injuries of the joint, and secondary arthritis is caused by the spread of purulent foci into the joint tissue, for example, mange, purulent endometritis, sepsis, pathogenic microbes, lymph from the tissue surrounding the joint. - formed by penetration through hematogenous routes. Purulent arthritis, as well as purulent synovitis, is caused by staphylococci, streptococci, Escherichia coli, blue bacillus and other pus-producing pathogens. [3]

I.A. Kalashnik (1990) and others say that arthritis in the early stages of development is rarely detected when animals are fed in a group. When it was possible to identify them early, it would be possible to prevent chronic purulent inflammations in the joints and tissues, which are considered very difficult to treat. [1]

In the article, etiopathogenesis of purulent conjunctivitis caused by conjunctivitis and its complications, methods of treatment with novocaine siege, execution methods and economic efficiency are shown. [6]

In the article, in addition to traditional methods for the treatment of keratoconjunctivitis in calves, when 3 ml of autoblood and 3 ml of 0.5% novocaine solution were mixed under the skin of the eyelids of the affected eyes, the morphological changes in their blood [7]

M.S. Borisov (2007) stated that in acute septic synovitis, visible changes in the blood are not noted. This is due to the rapid development of the inflammatory process in the joint area and the absence of microorganisms in the affected tissues. Significant changes can be observed only

when the synovium is examined by a laboratory. [4]

In the article. Linear dimensions and absolute values of coccyx during postnatal ontogeny of gray rabbits. [9]

In the article. The morphometric indicators of the muscles affecting the leg joint at different physiological stages of postnatal ontogenesis of sheep were studied and the characteristics of muscle changes at their physiological stages were studied. [10]

In the article. Some histological characteristics of the quadriceps muscles of the limb at different physiological stages of postnatal ontogenesis. [11]

In the article. The morphometric indicators of certain muscles acting on the joints of the pelvic organs in different physiological periods of postnatal ontogenesis of Hisar sheep living in different conditions were studied, and specific dynamics of changes depending on the anatomical and topographical conditions were determined. The extent of muscle activity and living conditions of animals. [12]

The morphometric indicators of some muscles acting on the joints of the proximal chest and pelvic organs in different physiological periods of postnatal

ontogenesis of Hisar sheep were studied, intensive growth of the indices up to 3 months was determined and the highest indicators were recorded. At 18 months, it is higher in sheep with sufficient conditions than in insufficient ones due to the direct influence of natural living conditions on the development dynamics of these muscle indicators, compared to other studied ages. [13]

According to A.V. Shadskaya (2010), despite the achievements of the pharmaceutical industry, today the problem of treating joint pathology in domestic animals remains very urgent. According to the author, synovitis is inflammation of the joint capsule. Etiological factors include closed and open joint injuries. Depending on the pathogen's impact on the body and the type of injury, injuries can be different. [8]

Conclusion: From the analysis of the literature, it can be concluded that arthritis is the most common joint disease in horses. This disease is characterized by purulent inflammation, and the formation of exudate occurs in the form of phlegmon and abscess, dystrophy and necrosis develop in the synovial sac and fascia. Purulent arthritis can be primary and secondary.

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